

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ADEDEJI****FIRST NAME: SIMISOLA****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 for Mac)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Why is it important to cite sources that provide information researchers use during research?
 - It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences
 - Everyone should mention the source of where the information they are writing about came from to give credit to the author¹**
 - Plagiarism is right and ethical
 - It is fair to take someone's work and not give them credit
2. All listed below are types of data sources except

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- Tertiary source
- Primordial source²**
- Primary source
- Secondary source

3. All listed below are components of an argument except

- Truth³**
- Claim
- Reason
- Warrant

4. The following are types of bibliographies except

- Single-author bibliography
- Annotated bibliography
- Achieved bibliography⁴**
- Selected bibliography

² Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 35–36.

³ Turabian, 58.

⁴ Turabian, 155.

5. When using the WHO style guide, Non-discriminatory languages should be used when referring to people except?

Designation⁵

Age

Disability

Gender

6. The following statements are correct except in the WHO style guide

In running text, give numbers zero to nine in words and 10 and higher in numbers

When a number is more than four digits, insert a space before every set of three digits counting from the right hand

For larger numbers, combine numerals and words

In running text, give numbers zero to nine in numbers and 10 and higher in words⁶

7. Philosophically, researchers make claims in four ways. They make claims about epistemology, axiology, methodology and

Ontology⁷

⁵ World Health Organization. 2013. *WHO Style Guide*. Second Edition. Geneva, Switzerland: WHO Headquarters, 55-56.

⁶ WHO, 26

⁷ Sampson, James P. 2017. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University. 146

- Sociology
- Ecology
- Biology

8. All are some of the ethical considerations for a qualitative study except

- Credibility
- Ability⁸**
- Anonymity
- Confidentiality

9. Below are examples of data collection methods for qualitative study except

- Interviews
- Incident reports
- Questionnaires⁹**
- Focus groups

10. The following are types of qualitative data analysis except

- Abductive analysis
- Conductive analysis¹⁰**

⁸ Sampson, 469-473.

⁹ Sampson, 469-475.

¹⁰ Sampson, 538.

- Deductive analysis
- Inductive analysis

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.